

LIGHTWEIGHT COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR RADIATION SHIELDING VIA ELECTROSPINNING FABRICATION

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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on the design and fabrication of innovative polymer-based radiation shields by using the electrospinning technique. A strategic architecture of the fibers is developed to enhance the radiation shielding properties of the composite material, and to preserve flexibility and adaptability to different surfaces. The polymer-based fibers are synthesized using a non-toxic solvent mixture, following a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach that avoids the use of conventional toxic solvents. The polymer concentration and solution formulation were optimized to ensure electrospinnability. The influence of electrospinning parameters (voltage, flow rate, and collector distance) on fiber morphology was systematically investigated. To explore potential improvements in shielding performance, high-Z lead-free fillers (Bi_2O_3 , Gd_2O_3 , and WO_3) were considered in simulation studies and theoretically evaluated for their photon attenuation efficiency when embedded in the polymer matrix. Photon attenuation properties were analyzed using the XCOM database across a wide energy range (0.001–10 MeV), relevant to space environments, including solar X-rays, solar gamma rays, and cosmic gamma radiation. Several experimental techniques were used to analyze the properties of the electrospun mats. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to investigate the chemical structure, while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) provided insights into the microfiber morphology. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out to evaluate the thermal properties of the electrospun fibers, also in consideration of the temperature fluctuations that are typically found during space exploration missions.

1 INTRODUCTION

As human space exploration advances toward longer and more complex missions, the development of advanced radiation shielding materials becomes increasingly critical to protect both astronauts and spacecraft electronics from the harmful effects of ionizing radiation [1]. This radiation arises primarily from solar particle events, solar-origin X-rays and γ -rays, and high-energy galactic cosmic rays, all of which pose cumulative biological and technological risks in low-Earth orbit and beyond [2]. Conventional shielding strategies have long relied on bulk metallic barriers, particularly lead, due to their high density and effective photon attenuation. However, such materials are inherently rigid, heavy, and environmentally hazardous, making them unsuitable for modern aerospace systems where weight constraints, flexibility, and sustainability are essential [3].

In response to these limitations, there is growing interest in the design of polymeric composite materials that combine lightweight polymer matrices with high-Z fillers capable of attenuating high-energy radiation [4]. This approach enables the fabrication of shielding materials that are not only mechanically adaptable but also engineered at the micro- or nanoscale to enhance radiation interaction cross-sections. Among advanced polymeric materials, polyimide (PI) stands out due to its exceptional

thermal and chemical stability, high mechanical strength, and inherent flexibility, making it a preferred material for aerospace applications [5-7].

Meanwhile, the pursuit of sustainable technologies has accelerated the replacement of toxic heavy metals with lead-free high-Z oxides, such as bismuth oxide (Bi_2O_3), gadolinium oxide (Gd_2O_3), and tungsten oxide (WO_3) [8, 9]. These materials offer high photon attenuation performance across broad energy ranges and have been increasingly explored for use in next-generation shielding composites [10]. To fabricate these advanced fibrous composite structures, electrospinning has emerged as a powerful and versatile fabrication method. This technique enables the production of uniform fiber mats with a high surface-area-to-volume ratio and allows for precise control over fiber morphology and architecture [11, 12]. Electrospinning is scalable from laboratory to industrial production, making it a promising route for large-scale production of lightweight shielding composites.

In the present work, polyimide fibers were successfully fabricated via electrospinning using non-toxic solvents and characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). To explore their applicability in radiation shielding, a simulation-based study was conducted to evaluate the theoretical performance of these fibrous structures when integrated with lead-free high-Z oxide fillers. Photon attenuation properties were calculated using the XCOM photon cross-section database over a wide energy range (0.001 to 10 MeV), encompassing the primary spectral domains of space radiation. The findings support the viability of these polyimide-based composites as lightweight and sustainable alternatives to conventional metallic shielding for future space missions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The following chemicals were obtained from the indicated sources and used without further purification: 2,2-bis [4-(4-aminophenoxy)phenyl] hexafluoropropane (4-BDAF, Tokyo Chemical Industry, Tokyo, Japan); 2,2-bis(3,4-dicarboxyphenyl) hexafluoropropane dianhydride (6FDA, Alfa Aesar, Kandel, Germany); dimethyl isosorbide (DMI, Sigma-Aldrich, Milan, Italy); acetone (ACS reagent, $\geq 99.5\%$); acetic anhydride (Chem-Lab, Zedelgem, Belgium) and pyridine (Honeywell Riedel-de Haën, Charlotte, NC, USA). Ultrapure water (resistivity 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\text{ cm}$) was obtained from a Direct-Q3 UV water purification system (Millipore, Molsheim, France).

2.2 Electrospinning

The polyimide (PI) used in this study was synthesized via a two-step process, as previously described in our earlier work [5]. After synthesis and purification, the resulting polyimide was obtained as a dry powder. The PI powder was dissolved in a solvent mixture of acetone and DMI at suitable ratio before the electrospinning process.

A custom-made experimental setup for electrospinning/electrospraying was employed to fabricate the polyimide fibers, providing precise control over process conditions and reproducibility [13-15]. A green electrospinning approach was employed by use of the non-toxic DMI/acetone solvent system. Process parameters (polymer concentration, solvent ratio, applied voltage, and flow rate) were optimized to yield uniform fibers. The optimized conditions, identified through preliminary screening, were applied throughout. Following electrospinning, the resulting fiber mats were subjected to thermal treatment at 150 °C for 2 hours to ensure complete removal of residual solvents and to promote further imidization of the polymer structure.

2.3 Characterization methods

The morphology of PI microfibers was examined via SEM (VEGA II LSH, Tescan, Czech Republic) after gold sputter-coating (Cressington 108, UK). Fiber diameter distribution was quantified using ImageJ (v1.51w) with the DiameterJ plugin (v1.018). Thermal behavior was assessed by DSC (Pyris DSC 8500, PerkinElmer, USA) under nitrogen flow (40 mL/min), using ~ 10 mg samples in sealed aluminum pans, scanned from 25 to 300 °C at 10 °C/min. FTIR analysis was performed with a Nicolet™

Summit spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped with a diamond ATR, recording spectra in the 4000–600 cm⁻¹ range at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution (64 scans, air background subtracted).

2.4 Radiation shielding simulations

Simulations of the composites radiation shielding properties were performed using the XCOM photon cross section database developed by NIST, incorporating total attenuation coefficients inclusive of coherent scattering [16]. The study focused on photon interactions within the 0.01–10 MeV energy range, encompassing the most relevant spectral domain for radiation exposure in low Earth orbit (LEO) and interplanetary space [17]. This range includes contributions from solar X-rays, gamma radiation from solar flares, and galactic cosmic photons, making it representative of operational space conditions [18]. Simulations were performed on pure polyimide (C₄₆H₁₂F₆O), high-Z oxides (PbO, Bi₂O₃, Gd₂O₃, and WO₃), and their corresponding composites with polyimide as the matrix. The selected fillers include lead oxide (PbO) as a conventional reference and three lead-free alternatives, bismuth oxide (Bi₂O₃), gadolinium oxide (Gd₂O₃), and tungsten oxide (WO₃), chosen for their high atomic numbers, chemical stability [19-21]. Two filler loadings (20 and 50 wt%) were selected as the most realistic concentrations, balancing processability, dispersion quality, and shielding effectiveness, under the assumption of uniform distribution within the polymer matrix. The total linear attenuation coefficient (μ) for each sample was calculated using the rule of mixtures, accounting for the weighted contributions of each component's mass attenuation coefficient (μ/ρ) and density. To assess the relative performance of the composites with respect to the neat polymer, a dimensionless attenuation ratio R was introduced, defined as:

$$R = \frac{(\mu/\rho)_{composite}}{(\mu/\rho)_{PI}} \quad (1)$$

where $(\mu/\rho)_{composite}$ is the mass attenuation coefficient of the filled system, and $(\mu/\rho)_{PI}$ is that of the pristine PI. This ratio, evaluated at a reference energy of 0.5 MeV, enables a direct and density-independent comparison of shielding efficiency across all compositions [22].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fabrication of PI microfibers by electrospinning

The electrospinning process was optimized by varying polymer concentration, solvent composition, voltage, and flow rate. Uniform fibers were obtained using a polyimide solution in a non-toxic binary DMI/acetone solvent system. The resulting mats were thermally treated at 150 °C for 2 h to remove residual solvents and promote further imidization. Figure 1a shows a representative SEM image of the thermally treated fibers, revealing smooth, bead-free, randomly oriented filaments. The corresponding diameter distribution (Fig. 1b), obtained using DiameterJ, resulted in a mean diameter of $1.16 \pm 0.59 \mu\text{m}$, with 36.9% porosity and an intersection density of 0.43 intersections/ μm^2 . This microstructure indicates a highly porous and interconnected architecture suitable for functional filler integration.

A qualitative assessment of flexibility is shown in Figure 1c. The mat was manually folded and released, demonstrating elastic recovery without visible damage or permanent deformation.

Figure 1: (a) SEM image of electrospun polyimide fibers after thermal treatment at 150 °C for 2 hours. (b) Fiber diameter distribution histogram. (c) Qualitative flexibility assessment: the mat is shown in its original state (left), after folding (middle), and following shape recovery (right).

3.2 Chemical and Thermal Properties of PI electrospun fibers

FTIR spectroscopy was employed to assess the chemical structure of electrospun polyimide fiber mats (20 wt%). Figure. 2a shows the chemical structure of aromatic PI with trifluoromethyl functional groups. The spectrum (Fig. 2b) exhibits well-defined imide-associated absorption bands, including the asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching vibrations at 1784 and 1724 cm^{-1} , respectively. The C=C stretching of the aromatic moiety is evident at 1504 cm^{-1} and remains unaltered. The absorption at 1379 cm^{-1} , assigned to C–N stretching, and the band at 724 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C=O bending, further corroborate the presence of the imide group. The absence of characteristic bands associated with unreacted amine and carboxylic acid groups (3330, 1710, 1650, and 1550 cm^{-1}) indicates a high conversion degree of poly (amic acid) into polyimide [5]. Minor features in the 2921–2850 cm^{-1} region are attributed to C–H stretching vibrations from residual solvent species.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was employed to evaluate the thermal behavior of electrospun PI fiber mats. The thermogram of the untreated fibers showed two distinct exothermic peaks at 220 °C and 232 °C during the heating (Fig. 2c). In contrast, the thermogram of the thermally treated PI fibers (150 °C for 2 h) does not exhibit any thermal events within the investigated temperature range, confirming the absence of residual transitions or structural rearrangements. The absence of thermal events up to 300 °C confirms the thermal stability of the treated fibers, making them suitable for aerospace applications requiring resistance to prolonged thermal exposure.

Figure 2: (a) Chemical structure of the in-house synthesized polyimide [5]. (b) FTIR spectra of electrospun PI fiber mats, untreated and thermally treated at 150 °C for 2 hours. Data are offset for clarity. (c) DSC thermograms of untreated and thermally treated PI fibers.

3.3 Simulations of radiation shielding capability

Figure 4 presents the simulated mass attenuation coefficients (μ/ρ) of the investigated fillers and polyimide-based composites across the 0.001–10 MeV photon energy range. As expected, PbO exhibited the highest attenuation due to its high atomic number. However, Bi₂O₃ demonstrated nearly equivalent performance, particularly within the 0.01–1 MeV range, which is highly relevant for shielding against solar and cosmic photon fluxes in low Earth orbit (LEO).

Upon incorporation into the PI matrix at 20 wt% and 50 wt% loading (Fig. 4c and 4e), all fillers led to an increase in attenuation relative to the pristine polymer. This effect becomes more pronounced at higher concentrations, with clear differences observed in the 0.1–1 MeV range (Figure. 4d and 4f), which corresponds to the energy window where Compton scattering dominates and shielding demands are most relevant to space radiation environments [23]. A comprehensive summary of the simulated mass attenuation coefficients (μ/ρ) at 0.5 MeV and the corresponding normalized attenuation ratios (R) relative to pristine PI is presented in Table 1. At 50 wt% filler loading, the Bi₂O₃-filled composite demonstrated superior attenuation performance compared to the PbO-based sample, with a marginally higher R value (1.416 vs 1.407).

Although composites incorporating WO₃ and Gd₂O₃ show comparatively lower R values, they still provide a significant improvement over unfilled polyimide. These results validate the role of high-Z oxide fillers in improving the photon-attenuation ability of polymer-based materials. In particular, Bi₂O₃ emerges as a very promising lead-free alternative that can offer attenuation performance equal to or marginally better than that of conventional lead-containing materials, while providing enhanced environmental sustainability and chemical stability features required for next-generation aerospace shielding materials.

Figure 4: Simulated photon attenuation of polyimide (PI) composites using XCOM. Total attenuation coefficients (0.001–10 MeV) were computed via the NIST XCOM database, including coherent scattering. Plots of (a,b) PbO and lead-free oxides (Bi₂O₃, Gd₂O₃, WO₃), (c, d) PI composites with 20 wt% fillers, (e, f) PI composites with 50 wt% fillers. (b, d, f) Enlarged area of plots showing the 0.1–1 MeV range relevant to LEO radiation environments.

Table 1: Attenuation performance of neat polyimide (PI) materials and polyimide composites at 0.5 MeV. Total attenuation coefficients (μ/ρ) and the corresponding normalized attenuation ratios (R) relative to neat PI calculated at 0.5 MeV using XCOM.

Sample	Total Attenuation (cm^2/g) at 0.5 MeV	R at 0.5 MeV
PI	0.086	1.000
PbO	0.161	1.875
Bi ₂ O ₃	0.158	1.831
Gd ₂ O ₃	0.110	1.283
WO ₃	0.127	1.480
PI/PbO (20 wt%)	0.100	1.163
PI/Bi ₂ O ₃ (20 wt%)	0.100	1.166
PI/Gd ₂ O ₃ (20 wt%)	0.091	1.057
PI/WO ₃ (20 wt%)	0.094	1.096
PI/PbO (50 wt%)	0.121	1.407
PI/Bi ₂ O ₃ (50 wt%)	0.122	1.416
PI/Gd ₂ O ₃ (50 wt%)	0.098	1.142
PI/WO ₃ (50 wt%)	0.107	1.240

4 CONCLUSIONS

Flexible polyimide-based fibrous mats were successfully fabricated via green electrospinning using a non-toxic solvent system and subsequently stabilized by heat treatment. The resulting materials exhibited uniform morphology, flexibility, and thermal stability up to 300 °C, confirming their suitability for use in space environment. A comprehensive characterization revealed smooth, bead-free fibers with a highly porous and interconnected microstructure. Radiation shielding simulations using XCOM demonstrated that PI composites loaded with lead-free high-Z oxides significantly enhance photon attenuation. Among the candidates, Bi₂O₃ showed performance comparable to or exceeding that of Pb, particularly in the 0.1–1 MeV range relevant to space radiation. These findings highlight the potential of PI/Bi₂O₃ composite mats as lightweight, flexible, and more sustainable alternatives to conventional shielding materials for future space missions.

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